

UDK 658.8

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TOOLS FOR ANALYSING MARKETING STRATEGIES IN A COMPANY

All companies in the market depend on the analysis of marketing strategies [1, 2]. At LEVTEL TRADE LLC, the main focus is on marketing strategy. The following points should be highlighted here: marketing is closely related to sales. A company constantly analyzes competitors and compares weaknesses, strengths, opportunities and threats. A SWOT analysis at LEVTEL TRADE LLC is conducted periodically, including software products (Table 1, 2).

Table 1 - The result of the assessment of strengths and threats of the software products sold by LEVTEL TRADE LLC

S - Strengths	W - Weak
1. Availability of customers in the trading business to whom you can sell CRM 2. Availability of the product (we deploy in a short time and carry out the first setup) + integration 3. Organic and paid advertising work well for attracting customers 4. Partially, CPA clients come through word of mouth 5. Cheap cost for stores with a large number of orders (the price depends only on the number of users) 6. Integration gives a powerful advantage - auto-calls,	1. Focusing only on incoming leads, which are mostly small businesses. Accordingly, there is a strong dependence on how many leads we have, and we are still heavily dependent on call centre sales. 2. Poor product knowledge of sales managers, it is necessary to prepare materials primarily for them (presentations, answers to frequently asked questions, differences from competitors). 3. Lack of long-term contracts (for a year or more) 4. The issue of data security and confidentiality is not well defined yet - any prolonged failure

<p>predicates, chats, chatbot, integration with managers</p> <p>7. Regular releases for the release of new functionality</p> <p>8. Implementation experience and some security approaches can be considered for CRM.</p>	<p>could significantly damage our reputation</p> <p>5. All the needs of the main target audience at the moment - online stores - are not covered</p> <p>6. CRM awareness is still in question.</p>
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As the analysis shows, the products began to be in great demand in the market after Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine. The company is now actively using these opportunities. By 2022, the company was a serious threat in the market, competing with Russian solutions. Of course, there are also threats, as any aggression or COVID causes market fluctuations, and the dollar peg affects customers' solvency.

Given these factors, it can be concluded that the success of LEVTEL TRADE LLC in developing marketing strategies and developing the company depends on the ability to adapt to changing market conditions, effectively use its strengths to minimise the impact of weaknesses and respond quickly to external opportunities and threats.

Table 2 - The result of the assessment of weaknesses and opportunities of the software products sold by LEVTEL TRADE LLC

O - Opportunities	T - Threats
<p>1. Ukrainian businesses need to replace Russian solutions (not everyone has given up yet), plus those looking for their first CRM are now considering mostly Ukrainian solutions (foreign ones do not have the necessary integrations)</p> <p>2. Social media and messengers are growing in popularity as channels of contact with customers, and</p>	<p>1. Highly competitive market for CRM systems, with Russian solutions still partially present (due to annual contracts or lack of alternatives - 1C)</p> <p>2. The reaction time of competitors to our changes is minimal (for example, the KeyCRM development cycle is a week)</p> <p>3. Competitors have more aggressive marketing, including active promotion through partners</p> <p>4. Limited demand and economic instability due to the war, in particular in</p>

requests should be processed not only manually but also through bots. 3. Businesses in most industries are launching fewer marketing campaigns, but are more actively monitoring their effectiveness. 4. Online shopping and manufacturing are recovering and expecting an increase in orders, with economic forecasts better than last year.	the field of valuation services, are still pessimistic. 5. Prices are fixed in dollars, so the price may increase significantly if the NBU exchange rate changes 6. The focus is now mostly on CPAs (this is the niche that attracts clients) 7. High cost of acquisition and low customer lifetime 8. Promotions with significant discounts attract insolvent customers.
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So, based on the analysis of Level Trade LLC, the company has great capabilities in terms of software products and the ability to quickly develop new features is their competitive advantage. Marketing strategy analysis and SWOT analysis are critical for understanding the market, making informed strategic decisions, managing risks, and maintaining competitive advantage [3, 4]. Marketing strategy analysis is the cornerstone of any successful marketing effort. Without it, companies would be essentially flying blind, making decisions based on guesswork rather than data and insights.

Information sources

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